

NURSES' ROLE IN THE PROCESS OF IDENTIFYING PATIENTS WITH SUSPECTED HEART ATTACKS

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Introduction: Acute Myocardial Infarction (AMI) is the most serious consequence of Acute Coronary Syndromes, which involves a spectrum of clinical signs and symptoms resulting from mechanical obstruction of blood flow, including chest pain as the main complaint reported. The professional nurse and the team play a fundamental role in the prognosis of the user who arrives at the emergency department with suspected AMI, through early recognition and appropriate management. **Objective:** To highlight the skills of nurses and staff in the early identification of acute myocardial infarction in emergency services, in order to anticipate care and favorable outcomes. **Methodology:** This is a literature review carried out in the first half of 2023, consulting the databases Virtual Health Library of the Ministry of Health, LILACS, BDENF and Google Scholar, using the DeCS: "Acute myocardial infarction"; "Nursing professionals"; and "Emergency". To develop the review, 11 scientific studies in Portuguese were selected through exploratory reading, using inclusion and exclusion criteria. The criteria used to select the studies were: articles published in the national literature whose main theme was the role of the professional nurse and team in dealing with the patient with suspected Acute Myocardial Infarction, between the years 2018 to 2023. **Results:** Due to the wide symptomatology of Acute Myocardial Infarction (AMI), it was evidenced that the clinical knowledge of the nurse shows itself as an essential factor facing the patient with suspected heart attack, since it is the professional to have the first contact with the user at the time of screening and will be able to distinguish the pain complaint presented. It is also important for the team to prepare and conduct the tests required by institutional chest pain protocols, such as performing an electrocardiogram and collecting biochemical markers of cardiac necrosis. Once a heart attack has been diagnosed, nursing care is provided during monitoring and caliber venous access, taking into account the severity of the AMI and the therapeutic window for thrombolytic therapy. **Conclusion:** As a result of the aspects mentioned above, it is important to note the importance of rapid decision-making by nurses who, based on specialized clinical knowledge, can stratify patients arriving at the emergency department with chest pain suggestive of acute myocardial infarction at an early stage, providing timely interventions.

Keywords: Acute myocardial infarction. Nursing professionals. Emergency.

Thematic area: Clinical Emergencies.